

ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INSECTICIDE USE FOR SUNFLOWER PROTECTION AGAINST COTTON BOLLWORM (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) IN THE SOUTHERN STEPPE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

*The purpose of this research is to determine the economic efficiency of protecting sunflower crops from the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) in the Southern Steppe of Ukraine. The experiments were carried out on the fields of the private farm "Terra" located in Odesa Oblast, Ukraine, during 2022–2023. Field experiments, comparative analysis, economic efficiency analysis, statistical data processing, and analytical methods were used. The highest profitability level (120.9%) was obtained with the application of Radiant® SC insecticide at a rate of 0.5 L/ha, indicating the feasibility of using this insecticide on sunflower crops under the conditions of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine. A high profitability level was also achieved with Belt 480 SC insecticide – 102.8%. Using the chemical insecticide Radiant® SC at a lower dose (0.3 l/ha) yielded the same level of profitability as Coragen® 20 SC – 93.5%. The highest gross income was obtained using the insecticide Radiant® SC at a dose of 0.5 l/ha – 1157 EUR/ha, which exceeded the option without insecticide application by 49.5%. Gross income from the use of Coragen® 20 SC, Ampligo 150 FC, and Belt 480 SC insecticides amounted to 926.43, 886.95, and 935.55 euro ha⁻¹, respectively, exceeding the control by 14.5–20.8%. The highest conditional net profit can be obtained by applying Radiant® SC insecticide at 0.5 L/ha – 633.53 thousand euro ha⁻¹, which is 304.97 thousand Euro ha⁻¹ or 92.9% higher than the option without protection against *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.*

Key words: sunflower, *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb., yield, economic efficiency, production cost, profitability

INTRODUCTION

A key objective for increasing the production of sunflower oilseed raw materials in Ukraine is to enhance seed yield by optimizing sowing areas, varietal resources, minimizing losses caused by harmful organisms, and improving the profitability of agricultural enterprises [2]. The production and marketing of sunflower

constitute a complex mechanism of relations between producers (sellers) and buyers, which requires the formation of optimal production and financial links between different zones and regions. These relations develop under the influence of many external factors, which, under the current economic conditions, also require in-depth study [1]. Despite its importance, the formation of the

sunflower market remains problematic due to the need to combine the tools of a free market and state regulation. This necessitates the development of mechanisms for its functioning, particularly at the regional level [10].

Sunflower yield formation occurs through complex biological mechanisms of interaction between plants and environmental conditions. The main groups of factors determining crop productivity include, on the one hand, the genetically determined properties of plants, and on the other – the conditions of their cultivation [19].

According to experts from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), by 2030, the entire global increase in crop production will be achieved primarily through new varieties and hybrids of crops, their new traits and characteristics. The introduction of new innovative sunflower hybrids into production – those highly responsive to fertilizer application, resistant to local disease and pest races, and tolerant to various environmental stresses – is one of the main reliable, economically beneficial, quickly paying off, and environmentally safe ways to increase productivity and achieve a high level of production stability. Therefore, at the current stage of agro-industrial development, the growing role of variety replacement is undeniable, as it is an important factor in intensifying seed production, improving quality indicators, reducing resource and energy consumption in technological processes, and protecting the environment from pollution by chemical inputs [3, 11, 12].

An important factor in improving the technology of growing sunflower seeds is the use of plant protection products, mineral and organic fertilizers, growth stimulants, and microbiological preparations. Forecasting the economic efficiency of growing sunflower should be carried out taking into account the balance of the cost of additional products and the cost of plant protection products, fertilizers, and microbiological preparations [8].

The high cost of energy resources in agricultural production is an obstacle to further improvement of crop production technologies. An important economically feasible direction for improving sunflower cultivation technology is the development of a set of measures that take into

account economic, environmental, and social aspects of production and market conditions [14].

The increase in yield and improvement in the quality of agricultural products depends on adequate zonal climate-oriented technology for growing agricultural crops. Stabilization of yield and profitability of production in the context of a trend towards rising prices for energy resources can be achieved through the use of resource-efficient technologies that combine a high level of agricultural technology, optimal plant nutrition, integrated plant protection systems against pathogens, insects, and weedy plants, as well as the introduction of new genotypes of varieties and hybrids. During the growing season, cultivated plants to various stress factors. The factors of influence are biotic and abiotic. Biotic stress is significantly spread by invasive alien plants, pests, and phytopathogens. Significant variability in crop productivity is caused by climate change, which causes droughts and destructive heavy rainfall. An increase in air temperature during the growing season also leads to temperature stress, soil moisture deficiency, and a decrease in yield [5, 18]. Competition between energy and food crops is increasing, which can lead to social tension in countries with a low standard of living [4].

The leading sector of global agri-food production is the cultivation and processing of oilseeds. Under current conditions of decline in livestock farming within Ukraine's agro-industrial complex, solving the problem of increasing the production of plant-based protein and oil is becoming increasingly important. Particular attention is paid to crops that are traditional to the country, especially oilseed crops. These crops are significant not only due to their tradition but also because they yield two valuable compounds – proteins and fats – within a single growing season. Depending on the crop, these may constitute 60–80% of the total harvest. Some oilseeds produce virtually no processing waste. As a result, oilseed crops demonstrate the highest growth rates in global agriculture. This economic situation necessitates an objective assessment of developments in the sector and highlights the need for in-depth research into the prospects for its further development and efficiency enhancement under new economic conditions. The problem of increasing the economic efficiency of sunflower seed production in Ukraine has been addressed by numerous

researchers, including well-known plant breeding researchers and economists, such as Kalenska et al. [6], Kuts and Makarchuk [7], Mateychuk [9], Tkachuk and Bondaruk [14].

Despite large-scale research and numerous publications, the issue of increasing the economic efficiency of sunflower seed production requires further study due to climate change, changing conditions of technical support for agricultural production, the entry into the market of innovative means of protection against harmful organisms, and hybrids with high productivity potential.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was conducted during 2022-2023. The purpose of the experiment is to develop methods for protecting sunflower crops from damage by the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.), to establish the economic efficiency of protection. The research was conducted on the experimental field of the private farm “Terra”, in the Odessa district of the Odessa region. Geographic coordinates of the experimental field: latitude – 46°28', longitude – 30°45'.

The soil-ecological zone of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine is characterized by hot, dry summers and mild, little-snowy, unstable winters. The climate combines features of both continental and maritime types.

According to the Odessa agrometeorological station [13], the average annual temperature is +11.1°C. The average January temperature is -1.8°C. The frost-free period lasts 166–208 days.

Annual precipitation ranges from 340 to 390 mm. The average annual relative humidity is 62%.

The soils of the farm are predominantly southern chernozems, heavy loam on loess-like deposits.

Soil analysis results: pH – 7.1, Humus content – 3.0%, Ammonium nitrogen (NH₄⁺) – 35 mg/kg, Nitrate nitrogen (NO₃⁻) – 2 mg/kg, Total mineral nitrogen – 91 mg/kg, Available phosphorus (P₂O₅) – 105 mg/kg, Available potassium (K₂O) – 62 mg/kg/

Thus, the soils in this region are typical for the agroecological zone of the Southern Steppe. They possess favorable physical and physicochemical properties, allowing for successful crop cultivation by enabling efficient accumulation and retention of soil moisture. Weather conditions during the experiments were typical for the agroecological zone of the Southern Steppe. Meteorological indicators during the study period are presented in Table 1.

The objective of the study was to determine the economic efficiency of sunflower protection against the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) during the crop's growing season and to assess the biological efficacy of the insecticide Radiant®, SC at different application rates compared to reference products Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150, FC, and Belt 480, SC.

Field trials of the insecticide Radiant®, SC were conducted in Odesa Oblast with application rates of 0.3 L/ha, 0.4 L/ha, and 0.5 L/ha on sunflower crops of the hybrid P64LC108, produced by Pioneer.

The sunflower hybrid P64LC108 is a mid-season, simple hybrid. The vegetation period is 120–125 days. Type – linoleic. It has high resistance to downy mildew. In parallel, the experiment included spraying plots with reference products: Coragen® 20 at a rate of 0.175 L/ha, Ampligo 150, FC – 0.3 L/ha, and Belt 480, SC – 0.15 L/ha (Table 2).

Table 1. Main Meteorological Indicators During the Research Period

Month	Average Daily Air Temperature, °C			Precipitation, mm			Relative Air Humidity, %		
	Long-term Average	2022	2023	Long-term Average	2022	2023	Long-term Average	2022	2023
Growing season total	17.2	19.15	19.73	234.0	141.1	242.1	67	68	67
April	9.0	9.4	10.0	34	12.6	116.5	72	74	73
May	15.1	16.3	16.6	39	11.4	4.6	69	70	74
June	19.4	22.3	21.3	42	30.7	33.2	67	69	66
July	21.4	23.9	23.8	49	6.2	47.8	64	62	68
August	21.2	24.8	25.3	34	24.3	40.0	63	66	63
September	17.1	18.2	21.4	36	55.9	0	68	67	60

Source: Data from the Odesa Agrometeorological Station [13].

The sowing method was wide-row. Row spacing was 70 cm, with 24 cm between plants in the row. Sowing depth: 5–6 cm. Sowing dates: in 2022 – May 5; in 2023 – April 29. The growth stage of the plants at the time of spraying: first – BBCH 65 (full flowering); second – BBCH 69 (end of flowering).

Table 2. Investigation scheme

Variant, Insecticide	Application Rate
1. Control, no treatment	-
2. Radiant®, SC	0.3 L/ha
3. Radiant®, SC	0.4 L/ha
4. Radiant®, SC	0.5 L/ha
5. Coragen® 20	0.175 L/ha
6. Ampligo 150, FC	0.3 L/ha
7. Belt 480, SC	0.15 L/ha

Source: Own calculation.

Agrotechnical conditions of the test plots: predecessor – winter wheat; fertilizer rate – N16P16K16, applied simultaneously with sowing.

Total plot area – 46.2 m²; accounting area – 30.8 m²; layout – randomized blocks; number of replications – 4.

Application method: spraying during the crop's vegetation period. Equipment used:

boom sprayer of compressor type, manufactured by Euro-Pulve, “bicycle” trolley model; spray nozzle marking – Tee Jet 1 XR 11003-VP. Working fluid rate: 250 L/ha; working pressure: 3.0 kPa/atm. Number of nozzles – 6; sprayer boom width – 3 m; distance between nozzles on the boom – 50 sm; boom height above crop canopy – 50 cm.

All assessments were carried out in accordance with widely recognized methodologies [15, 16, 17].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The yield level of any crop, including sunflower, is primarily determined by key structural indicators such as the 1000-seed weight, head diameter, and seed output per head. It was found that the application of different insecticides at varying application rates in this experiment influenced both yield structure indicators and the morphological and biometric characteristics of sunflower plants (Table 3).

Table 3. Effect of insecticides on structural yield components and biometric indicators of sunflower depending on the plant protection product used

Application Variant	Application Rate, L/ha	Average Stem Diameter, cm,	Average Number of Green Leaves per Plant, pcs	Plant Height at Flowering Stage, cm	Average Head Diameter, cm
Control, no treatment	-	1.66	15.40	188.60	14.35
Radiant®, SC	0.3	1.73	16.10	190.10	15.84
Radiant®, SC	0.4	1.81	16.60	191.45	16.25
Radiant®, SC	0.5	2.09	16.45	190.10	16.80
Coragen® 20	0.175	1.72	16.10	189.03	15.85
Ampligo 150, FC	0.3	1.70	16.10	190.70	15.90
Belt 480, SC	0.15	1.71	15.90	190.48	15.85

Source: Own calculation.

During the assessment, differences in the number of live leaves per plant were observed across all experimental treatments. The highest number of remaining live leaves was recorded in the treatment with Radiant®, SC at 0.5 L/ha, which exceeded the control by 1.2 leaves, averaging 16.45 leaves per plant. In this treatment, sunflower plants also exhibited a larger head diameter compared to other treatments and the control. The head diameter in this variant was 2.45 cm greater than in the untreated control.

At harvest, sunflower heads were collected

from an area of 10 m² from each treatment and then threshed to determine seed yield and for subsequent laboratory analysis. In laboratory conditions, the threshed samples were weighed, cleaned, and analyzed to determine the 1,000-seed weight, seed moisture content, and oil content.

In all insecticide-treated variants, an increase in seed mass after threshing was observed compared to the control (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of insecticides on sunflower seed mass after threshing and cleaning

Protection Variant	Application Rate, L/ha	Plant Density Before Harvest, thousand/ha	Seed Mass from 10 m ² After Threshing, g	Seed Mass from 10 m ² After Cleaning, g
Control, no treatment	–	53	4,045.2	2,558.5
Radiant®, SC	0.3	55	4,207.5	2,994.7
Radiant®, SC	0.4	54	4,437.4	3,190.0
Radiant®, SC	0.5	54	5,043.6	3,819.1
Coragen® 20	0.175	50	4,446.0	3,055.0
Ampligo 150, FC	0.3	52	3,707.6	2,926.3
Belt 480, SC	0.15	52	4,615.0	3,083.6

Source: Own calculation.

The highest sample mass per 10 m² after threshing and seed cleaning was recorded in the Radiant®, SC at 0.5 L/ha treatment—3,819.1 g, while the control treatment yielded only 2,558.5 g.

The results of the laboratory analysis indicate that the use of insecticides in this study led to an increase in the 1,000-seed weight across all treatments (Table 5).

Table 5. Laboratory analysis indicators of sunflower seeds under different plant protection treatments

Application Variant	Application Rate, L/ha	Thousand Seed Weight, g	Thousand Seed Weight (Dry Matter), g	Seed Moisture Content, %	Oil Content in Seeds, %
Control, no treatment	–	45.29	42.55	6.06	43.63
Radiant®, SC	0.3	48.37	45.58	5.78	43.72
Radiant®, SC	0.4	50.88	47.46	6.73	43.65
Radiant®, SC	0.5	50.66	47.65	5.91	44.73
Coragen® 20	0.175	50.61	47.57	6.01	44.14
Ampligo 150, FC	0.3	49.24	46.21	5.78	43.72
Belt 480, SC	0.15	47.37	44.34	6.40	43.80

Source: Own calculation.

The highest 1,000-seed weight adjusted to dry matter was recorded for the treatments with Radiant®, SC (0.5 L/ha) – 47.65 g and Coragen® 20 (0.75 L/ha) – 47.57 g, while the untreated control variant had a weight of 42.55 g.

In the control variant, the oil content was 43.63%. In the treatment with Ampligo 150, FC, this indicator increased to 43.72%. In the experimental variant using Belt 480, SC, the oil content also rose to 43.80% compared to the control.

The maximum increase in oil content was observed with the application of Radiant®, SC at a rate of 0.5 L/ha, showing an increase of 1.10%.

The seed moisture content in the control variant was 6.06%. Meanwhile, the highest moisture levels were recorded in the treatments with Belt 480, SC and Radiant®, SC, ranging from 6.40% to 6.73%. The lowest seed moisture was observed in the treatments with Ampligo 150, FC and Radiant®, SC at a rate of 0.3 L/ha – 5.78%.

The research results demonstrated that the food quality of sunflower seeds significantly depends on the use of insecticides.

It was found that insecticide application

positively influenced the formation of quality seed parameters in sunflower.

Thus, optimizing cultivation technology through insecticide application contributes to achieving high sunflower seed yields and improves the biochemical indicators of the grain's food quality.

Our results indicate that the use of insecticides for the protection of sunflower against cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) contributed to a yield increase of 0.37–1.26 t/ha (Table 6).

The highest sunflower seed yield was obtained in the variant treated with Radiant®, SC at 0.5 L/ha – 3.81 t/ha, whereas the yield in the untreated control was 2.55 t/ha. Treatment of sunflower crops with insecticides Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150, FC and Belt 480 increased sunflower seed yield.

The final result of improving the elements of sunflower seed production technology should be an assessment of the economic efficiency of the proposed elements - increased yield, cost of production, additional income, net profit.

An assessment of the economic efficiency of the use of innovative insecticides to combat the cotton bollworm - Radiant® SC, Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150 FC and Belt 480 SC showed that the use of

the insecticide Radiant® SC at a rate of 0.5 l/ha on sunflower crops to combat the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) was the most

appropriate. Other insecticides had a lesser effect on the preservation of yield and seed quality.

Table 6. Economic efficiency of using various insecticides on sunflower crops against *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb

Performance indicators	Insecticide Application Variants						
	Control, no treatment	Radiant®, SC, 0.3 L/ha	Radiant®, SC, 0.4 L/ha	Radiant®, SC, 0.5 L/ha	Coragen® 20, 0.75 L/ha	Ampligo 150, FC, 0.3 L/ha	Belt 480, SC, 0.150 L/ha
Average yield, t·ha ⁻¹	2.55	2.99	3.19	3.81	3.05	2.92	3.08
Price of seeds, euro·t ⁻¹	303.7	303.7	303.7	303.7	303.7	303.7	303.7
Gross product, euro·ha ⁻¹	774.5	908.2	968.9	1,157.2	926.4	886.9	935.5
Production costs, euro·ha ⁻¹	446.0	469.2	471.9	523.7	476.7	465.0	461.2
Cost, euro·t ⁻¹	174.9	156.9	147.9	137.4	156.3	159.2	149.7
Net operating profit, euro·ha ⁻¹	328.5	438.9	497.0	633.5	449.6	421.9	474.3
Profitability level, %	73.6	93.5	105.3	120.9	94.3	88.5	102.8

Source: Author's estimated based on Field Survey, 2022–2023.

The insecticide Radiant® SC at a dose of 0.5 l/ha on sunflower crops in the conditions of the Southern Steppe of Ukraine showed the highest level of profitability - 120.9%, which indicates a significant potential for increasing the economic efficiency of sunflower production through the use of innovative means of protection against harmful insects. A high profitability level was also reached with Belt 480 SC – 102.8%. At a lower application rate (0.3 l/ha), Radiant® SC insecticide showed a level of profitability comparable to Coragen® 20 SC insecticide – 93.5%.

The maximum gross income was obtained from the application of Radiant® SC at a rate of 0.5 l/ha – 1157 €·ha⁻¹, which exceeded the control (untreated) by 49.5%. The gross income from the use of Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150 FC and Belt 480 SC insecticides was 926, 886 and 935 €·ha⁻¹ respectively, exceeding the standard by 14.5 – 20.8%.

A generalized indicator of the effectiveness of innovative technological measures is the net profit obtained from the studied agricultural techniques. The highest net profit was achieved when using Radiant® SC at a dose of 0.5 l/ha – 633€·ha⁻¹, which is 304 €·ha⁻¹, or 92.9%, more than in the untreated version without plant protection against *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.

CONCLUSIONS

The highest gross profit was obtained when using Radiant®, SC at a rate of 0.5 l/ha –

1157 €·ha⁻¹, which exceeded the control (without insecticide treatment) by 49.5%. The gross profit from the use of insecticides Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150, FC and Belt 480, SC amounted to 926, 886 and 935 €·ha⁻¹, respectively, exceeding the control (without insecticide treatment) by 14.5–20.8%.

The highest profitability was achieved when using the drug Radiant®, SC at a rate of 0.5 l/ha – 120.9%, which indicates the feasibility of using this insecticide on sunflower crops in the Southern Steppe of Ukraine. A high level of profitability was also achieved when using the drug Belt 480, SC – 102.8%.

The highest conditional net profit was achieved when using the insecticide Radiant®, SC at a rate of 0.5 l/ha – 633 €·ha⁻¹, which is 304 €·ha⁻¹ or 92.9% more than in the control without insecticide treatment (without protection against *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.).

Application of Radiant®, SC at a lower rate (0.3 L/ha) resulted in a profitability level comparable to that of Coragen® 20 – 93.5%.

The food quality of sunflower seeds significantly depended on the use of insecticides to control *Helicoverpa armigera* Hb. The highest 1,000 seed weight of the P64LC108 hybrid sunflower (calculated as dry matter) was recorded in the variants treated with the insecticide Radiant®, SC (0.5 l/ha) – 47.65 g and Coragen® 20 (0.75 l/ha) – 47.57 g, while the untreated control had a 1000 seed weight of 42.55 g. The maximum increase in seed oil content (by 1.10%) was achieved when Radiant®, SC was applied at a dose of 0.5 l/ha.

The use of insecticides to protect sunflower from the cotton bollworm (*Helicoverpa armigera* Hb.) led to an increase in yield by 0.37–1.26 t/ha. The highest sunflower seed yield was obtained on the variant treated with Radiant®, SC at a dose of 0.5 l/ha – 3.81 t/ha, while the yield in the untreated control (without insecticides) was 2.55 t/ha.

Application of Coragen® 20, Ampligo 150, FC, and Belt 480, SC increased sunflower seed yield by 0.37–0.53 t·ha⁻¹, or 14.5–20.8%.

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